

OpenStreetMap as a tool for skill building

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OpenStreetMap, the crowdsourced geospatial database, currently has over eight million registered members [1]. This makes it one of the largest VGI projects with proven multifaceted use cases, e.g. post-disaster response, combating female genital mutilation, app development, and navigation. Its contributors wholly make and maintain the database, making all decisions without a top-down governing authority. Generally, OSM mapping is regarded as a form of volunteering to create freely accessible geodata. However, recent studies suggest that experience gained through the mapping process could be equally important as well [2–4]. Building on the existing body of knowledge, in this talk, we will share the findings of our research on the effects of OSM mapping on young mappers.

We studied a youth mapping internship called Digital Internship and Leadership (DIAL) conducted in three cohorts. The cohorts were composed of 3 males and 5 females in cohort I, 12 males and 7 females in cohort II and 8 males and 2 females in cohort III. They were originally from different places but were living in Kathmandu and Pokhara. They were university level students studying business administration, crisis management, architecture, public health, computer science, and geomatics engineering. We chose this internship program for its inclusiveness in terms of academia, gender, and the geographical locations that the participants came from. The program was designed and executed by Kathmandu Living Labs (KLL) and funded by the National Academy of Sciences under the PEER Science Project. It was designed to fill critical map data gaps in rural Nepal through youths. Participant mappers were called through an open invitation on social media. They filled an application through an online form, which comprised questions regarding backgrounds and interests. The short-listed recent high school graduates and undergraduate students were from diverse academic backgrounds (geomatics engineering, architecture, crisis management, management, forestry, computer science and engineering, electronics engineering, management, public health, mechanical engineering). The participant mappers were trained in person for 3-4 days. They were oriented on remote mapping (Java OpenStreetMap and iD Editor), field mapping (OSM Tracker for Android, Field Papers), and geospatial data visualization (Carto) during the orientation.

We studied the self-assessed experiences of the participant mappers at two different points of time: (i) during the mapping program (ii) after two years for Cohorts II and

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III, and three years for Cohort I. Short-term effects were studied through grounded theory coding of reports and blogs documented by all the participants during the internship period. Each participant had prepared at least one blog and one report each to document their experiences of mapping. These reports were collected from the participant mappers at the end of the internship and the blogs were written throughout the internship. The reports were written in a fixed format, whereas the blogs were flexible. The format of the report comprised an introduction to digital internship, process, outcome, and evaluation of the impact of their work, reflections on the personal and professional learning and growth emerging from the internship, and recommendations. For long-term impacts, an online survey administered to identify if the effects persisted. An online questionnaire was administered via Google forms to assess the extent to which effects reported during the mapping period persisted and whether others emerged. Questions were derived from the literature and based on analyses of the reports and blogs. The survey assessed learning in areas of affective learning, production of geography-based knowledge, networking and social skills development, technical skills and digital literacy, professional skill-building, cognitive skills and civic skills. All the participant mappers of DIAL were approached for the survey. The questionnaire was sent through email and google form and was self-administered. The response rate was 72.5%. First, we used descriptive statistics to summarise and describe the answers to each question, this consisted of calculating the frequency and mode of each data. The outliers were calculated through the interquartile range. The distinction in academia between geography, geomatics, and the others and its plausible effect on the long-term impacts were tracked through multivariate analysis.

Results show OSM mapping helps the mappers develop several vital skill sets and expand their knowledge in a variety of areas. Some of them are: deepening of civic engagement, development of social identity, expansion of geographic knowledge, spatial awareness, increase in happiness and satisfaction. They retain most of these skills even in the long run, irrespective of differences in academic or professional backgrounds. Surprisingly, 44.8% of the participants cited they considered being a professional mapper or cartographer at some point in time because of their experience in DIAL. The same people report that OSM mapping increased their belief in their ability to help society.

Our findings build upon the studies of the use of OSM in high schools, which was noted to increase creativity and spatial awareness among the students [2,3,5]. When compared to Ebrahim et al.'s study with ten-year-olds [3], the similarity in findings suggests these developments might be similar across ages. These developments suggest new directions toward the use of OSM as a tool for youth skill building and youth community engagement and design newer incentive mechanism for people to join and retain in OSM. 55.2% of the survey participants said that they continued to map in OSM after the internship. Reasons for discontinuation of mapping included absence of peer group, lack of time, lack of incentive, lack of interest and absence of recognition. Reasons for continuation to map included professional alignment to mapping, humanitarianism, social responsibility, interest to map, useability of the OSM data among others.

There is still a huge scope of investigation left in this area, ideally through a longitudinal study with a bigger and more diverse sample and comparisons between different program designs, to fully understand the wide array of effects of OSM mapping on the mappers, as well as the potential to deepen positive outcomes via associated youth learning and leadership programs. There are undoubtedly other categories of benefits of

OSM mapping that is yet to be identified. Hence, it is worthwhile to reconsider the idea of participatory mapping and related programs, and their effects on the contributing mappers.

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